

Effect of Fortification of Collagen Extract from Chicken Feet Skin Fermented by *L.Plantarum* on the Properties of Beef Meatballs

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Abstract

One of the efforts to improve the properties of meatballs is to add certain ingredients. Collagen extract which is a derivative product of protein is thought to improve the properties of beef meatballs. The properties of collagen extract as an additive can be enriched by fermentation using lactic acid bacteria (LAB) such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* (*L.plantarum*). The purpose of this study was to evaluate the use of fortification of collagen extract of chicken feet skin fermented by *L. plantarum* bacteria on the properties of beef meatballs. The main ingredients use Balinese beef. Collagen extract is derived from the extraction of the skin of broiler chicken feet fermented using *L.plantarum* bacteria. A total of 6 treatment combinations were applied in this study, namely fortification of collagen extract: M_1 = without fermentation Vs 2%); M_2 = without fermentation vs 4%); M_3 = without fermentation Vs 6%); M_4 = fermented by *L.Plantarum* Vs 2%); M_5 = fermented by *L.Plantarum* Vs 4%); M_6 = fermented by *L.Plantarum* Vs 6%. The results showed that there was no effect on pH, cooking loss, water holding capacity and consumer perceptions of beef meatball products using collagen extract from chicken feet skin (CFS), both fermented using *L.Plantarum* and without fermentation using *L.Plantarum*. Likewise, differences in the level of use of collagen extract did not have an effect on the properties (pH, cooking loss, water holding capacity and preference) of beef meatball products. In the case of fortification of beef meatballs using collagen extract, there is no need for bacterial fermentation of *L. Plantarum* as an efficiency option with a minimum level of 2% (M_1 treatment).

Keywords: Meatball; beef, collagen; chicken feet skin (CFS); *L.plantarum*

Introduction

The need for animal food is increasing along with the increasing world population. The need for processed food products from meat is increasingly in demand by most people in the world. Processed food is made as an effort to diversify food products. One of the processed products from meat that is commonly consumed by the world's population is meatballs. Meatballs are one type of processed meat product that is very popular with people in Indonesia. Not only in Indonesia, even this product is also a favorite food for people in almost all countries in the world.

The quality of meatballs is strongly influenced by the manufacturing process and the type of material used. One of the problems in the process of making meatballs is the imperfect emulsification process. The emulsification process is influenced by the processing method and the composition of the materials used. One type of additive that can be used to improve the emulsification process is collagen extract. Collagen is a type of product derived from protein obtained from the partial hydrolysis of animal body parts. One part of the animal body that is very rich in collagen is the skin organ (Gordon and Hahn, 2010; Ikoma, 2003).

Chicken feet is one type of by-product of poultry that has not been utilized so far. Chicken feet are protected by skin which is mostly composed of collagen components. According to Meng et al., (2019), the use of collagen from non-mammal animals has been widely applied in the food industry. Collagen is rich in

nutrients because it contains a large number of amino acids, especially the amino acids glycine, proline and hydroxyproline. Collagen structure is mostly composed of amino acid components which are thought to improve the properties of processed meat, especially the emulsification process. In addition, collagen also contains a number of other components that can increase the nutritional value of a processed meat product. Collagen can be fortified into meatball dough to improve its properties.

The fermentation process using *Lactobacillus plantarum* (*L.plantarum*) bacteria, the collagen extract production process is one of the efforts to make functional food. *L.plantarum* which is classified as lactic acid bacteria (LAB) which has the ability to produce lactic acid and proteolytic enzymes (Mugampoza et al., 2019; Wikandari et al., 2012). The lactic acid component functions as a preservative and can inhibit the growth of contaminant microorganisms (Daeschel, 1989). This study aims to evaluate the effect of fortification of collagen extract from chicken feet skin (CFS) that has been fermented using *L.plantarum* bacteria into the dough on the properties of beef meatballs.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The main ingredients used in this study were beef from Bali cattle, male, aged between 2-3 years, from the *Biceps femoris* muscle. Bali beef was obtained from the Tamangapa Slaughterhouse, Antang, Makassar, Indonesia. The raw material for collagen is chicken feet skin obtained from the Daya traditional market, Makassar, Indonesia. The raw material for chicken feet comes from broiler types with a slaughter age of 45 days. Bacterial isolates of *L.plantarum* were obtained from the Microbiology Laboratory, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. Supporting equipment used include: electric oven (*Memmert 100-800*), water bath (*Memmert*), Filter Paper Press (Modification), pH meter (*Lutren PH-201*), analytical balance.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Preparation process of chicken feet skin (CFS)

A total of 4 kg of chicken feet samples were prepared for preparation. The prepared chicken feet were selected from chickens in healthy condition with bright feet color (yellowish white). Chicken feet are washed with running water for 3 minutes. The skin organ was separated from the bone of the chicken feet using a sterile knife. The separation process starts from the base of the foot near the joint (patella os) and ends at the sole of the foot. The skin of the chicken feet was washed with running water for 3 minutes. Then it was weighed and dried in the oven at 50°C for 24 hours.

2.2.2. Production process of collagen extract

A total of 300 g of CFS samples were put into 1000 mL of distilled water. A total of 52% isolates of *L.plantarum* bacteria inoculated into the aquadest. The process of fermenting the CFS in a solution of *L.plantarum* bacteria was carried out for 3 days at room temperature. The fermentation process carried out using a sheker as a means of the fermentation process. *L.plantarum* bacteria inactivated on skin samples in an oven for 2 hours at 60°C. The CFS sample was removed from the bacterial solution and then put into a beaker glass containing 200 mL of distilled water. The beaker glass containing the CFS sample was put into a water bath. The extraction process carried out for 24 hours at a temperature of 60°C. The CFS sample was filtered using a flannel cloth. The filtering results obtained a liquid collagen extract. Liquid collagen extract is put into a bottle to be applied to the meatball dough.

2.2.3. Fortification collagen extract in meatball dough

A total of 150 g of beef grounded using a food processor. Ground beef is added with complementary ingredients such as: tapioca flour (50 g); onion (1 g); garlic (4 g); ground pepper (0.5 g); salt (4.5 g); granulated sugar (1 g); egg white (25 g); flavoring (0.5 g) and ice crystals (30 g). The dough added with collagen extract (each according to treatment). The dough molded to form meatballs and then cooked.

2.2.4. Research design and data analysis

The study was designed using a completely randomized design (CRD) with a factorial pattern. A total of 6 treatment combinations were applied in this study. M₁ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 2%); M₂ = collagen extract without fermentation (4% level); M₃ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 6%); M₄ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 2%); M₅ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 4%); M₆ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 6%). Data were analyzed statistically using ANOVA. The results of the analysis that showed a significant effect were then tested using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a level of 5% (Steel and Torrie, 1991).

Results and Discussion

pH value

According to Aberle et al., (2001), one of the important characteristics of processed meat products is the pH value. Many things affect the pH value of processed meat products. This is related to the condition of the meat from the livestock used. Several factors that affect the pH value are: stress level on livestock, method used in slaughtering and condition of livestock at rest. Under normal conditions, the pH of meat is in the range of 5.4-5.8. This condition occurs 6 hours after slaughtering cattle. This condition causes the meat to be bright red in color. Collagen extract fortification may affect the pH conditions of the resulting meatball product. Comparison of the pH value of beef meatball products on different combinations of fortification treatments is clearly presented in Figure 1.

The results of the test using ANOVA data in Figure 1 show that the difference in the combination of fortification treatment types of collagen extract with the level of use of collagen extract did not have a significant effect ($p>0.05$) on the pH value of beef meatballs. Based on these data, it can be seen that, although statistically it does not show a significant effect, on average the treatment combination M₄-M₆ (5.83-5.90) has a lower average pH value than M₁-M₃ (6.13 -6.20). The difference in the pH value of the two combinations was caused by the different types of collagen extract fortified into the dough.

Fig 1. Comparison of the pH value of beef meatball products in the combination of fortification treatment of collagen extract types and different levels; M₁ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 2%) ; M₂ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 4%); M₃ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 6%); M₄ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 2%); M₅ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 4%); M₆ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 6%)

The combination of M₄-M₆ treatment showed a lower pH because it used collagen extract that had been fermented using *L.plantarum* bacteria. The *L.plantarum* bacteria is one type of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) which can produce acidic compounds. According to Lerena et al., (2016), organic acids can be metabolized by *L. plantarum*. The results of fermentation in the form of carbon will be used by bacteria as an energy source. Furthermore, by Ge et al., (2019), it was explained that the protein oxidation process was

able to be significantly inhibited by *L.plantarum*. Furthermore, Mousavi and Mousavi (2019) and Hur et al., (2014) explain that the pH value is influenced by the production of these organic acids. During fermentation, *L.plantarum* bacteria can liberate phenolic compounds which will affect antioxidant activity.

Fortification of collagen extracts containing acidic compounds can cause the product to have a low pH. On the other hand, the fortification of collagen extract with a combination of M₁-M₃ treatments produced meatball products with a pH that tends to be close to neutral.

Cooking loss (CL)

Cooking loss is the percentage of meat weight lost due to the cooking process. This parameter is a function of cooking time and temperature. Meat with low cooking loss has a relatively better quality than meat with a high percentage of cooking loss. Meat products with high cooking losses can cause nutritional losses to be even greater (Komariah, 2009). Comparison of the combination of collagen extract fortification treatments with different types and levels of use of collagen extract is presented in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Comparison of the cooking loss (%) of beef meatball products in the combination of fortification treatment of collagen extract types and different levels; M₁ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 2%) ; M₂ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 4%); M₃ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 6%); M₄ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 2%); M₅ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 4%); M₆ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 6%)

Based on the data in Figure 2, the results of statistical analysis are obtained. The results of statistical analysis showed that the difference in the combination of collagen extract types with the level of collagen extract did not show a significant effect ($p>0.05$) on the cooking loss parameter. In Figure 2 it can be seen that, the combination of using fermented collagen extract with *L.plantarum* bacteria on average resulted in a relatively higher cooking loss than the use of unfermented collagen extract. This may be due to the fact that in the fermentation process using *L.plantarum* bacteria, the collagen extract underwent structural changes so that it was unable to provide a positive effect in maintaining cooking loss in meatball products. The highest cooking loss was in treatment M₄ (16.26%±5.08) and the lowest cooking loss was M₁ (8.06±1.61%).

According to Soeparno (2009), the amount of cooking loss is influenced by pH, length of muscle fiber sarcomere, length of muscle fiber cut, myofibril contraction status, size and weight of meat samples and cross-section of meat. According to Battacharya et al., (2016), meat quality, especially related to functional properties, can be influenced by stress conditions in livestock. Stress conditions can occur during cutting. The proteolytic activity carried out by *L.plantarum* bacteria affects the physical properties of processed meat. According to Zhou et al., (2019), that the actin and sarcoplasmic proteins can undergo a denaturation process, where there is a transformation from a helical shape to a sheet form. Furthermore, Wang et al, (2019) explained that the process of merging two molecules of protein compounds is influenced

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by the presence of processes in the form of hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic forces and the occurrence of electrostatic interactions. It was clarified again by Wang et al., (2018), that the process of high surface hydrophobicity, the process of protein solubility in water certainly plays a very important role. These statements are supported by Rahaman et al., (2016), protein immunoreactivity is influenced by the presence of processes in its primary structure. As a result of these changes, the protein can undergo a process of degradation, aggregation, folding and cross-linking.

Water Holding Capacity (WHC)

According to Lawrie (2003), meat protein plays a role in binding water to meat. High protein content of meat can increase the WHC of meat, and this will reduce the free water content, conversely, the higher the amount of water that comes out, the water binding capacity will also decrease. The comparison of the combination of treatments using collagen extract in beef meatballs based on the type and level is clearly presented in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Comparison of the water holding capacity (%) of beef meatball products in the combination of fortification treatment of collagen extract types and different levels; M₁ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 2%) ; M₂ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 4%) ; M₃ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 6%) ; M₄ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 2%) ; M₅ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 4%) ; M₆ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 6%)

Based on the ANOVA results, the data in Figure 3 shows that the difference in the combination of the use of collagen extract as a fortificant in beef meatball products does not show a significant effect ($p>0.05$) on the WHC parameter. On average, the WHC value is in the range of 66.86%-69.33%. WHC value is closely related to CL. The higher the WHC value in a meat product, the lower the CL tends to be. According to Kandeepan et al., (2013), the WHC value is influenced by the protein content of the meat. Furthermore, Rowe et al., (2004) explained that the protein oxidation process plays an important role in influencing the WHC value. Furthermore, Xiong et al. (2000) explained that, in addition to WHC, the protein oxidation process is also related to other functional properties such as the emulsion process, gel formation, tenderness and wetness properties.

Consumer perception (hedonic test)

The acceptability of meat products for consumers is influenced by several factors, including depending on the texture, flavor and taste (Soeparno, 2009). Consumer acceptance of a product greatly determines the selling power of a product. The composition of ingredients and formulas used in making a product will greatly affect the level of consumer preference for a product. Comparison of consumer perceptions on beef meatball products fortified with collagen extract by combining the types and levels of collagen extract in full is presented in Figure 4.

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Fig 4. Comparison of the consumer perception of beef meatball products in the combination of fortification treatment of collagen extract types and different levels; M₁ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 2%) ; M₂ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 4%); M₃ = collagen extract without fermentation (level 6%); M₄ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 2%); M₅ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 4%); M₆ = collagen extract fermented with *L.Plantarum* bacteria (level 6%); consumer rating scale 1-6 (dislike-very like)

Based on ANOVA, the data shown in Figure 4 shows that there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in consumer perceptions regarding preference for beef meatball products that have been fortified with collagen extract with different combinations of types and levels. These results indicate that the fermentation process using LAB *L.plantarum* on collagen extract has no effect on consumer acceptance. The level of preference is directly proportional to the consumer's acceptance. Consumer acceptance will tend to increase if the level of consumer preference also increases. According to Winarno et al., (1980), additives are materials that are intentionally added or given to a product with a specific purpose and purpose. The aim is to improve consistency, nutritional value, taste, control acidity and alkalinity and improve shape, texture and appearance. Furthermore, Forrest et al (1975) stated that the addition of fillers is intended to reduce shrinkage during cooking, improve emulsion stability, improve taste, improve slice properties and reduce production costs.

Conclusion

Fortification of materials using collagen extracts with different combinations of types and levels did not affect the pH value, CL, WHC and consumer perceptions of beef meatball products. The use of *L.plantarum* fermented bacteria in the fermentation process of CFS to produce collagen extract did not affect pH, CL, WHC and consumer perceptions of beef meatballs. The use of *L.plantarum* bacteria in the collagen extract fermentation process is not needed in the fortification process of beef meatball products. In addition, the use of collagen extract is still selected which uses the lowest level (M₁ treatment).

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Conflict of Interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest

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